

A new DSC-based method to determine the wax porosity of mixtures precipitated from crude oils

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Abstract

Wax precipitation is one of the most important problems in flow assurance. The correct prediction of the wax appearance temperature (WAT) and the wax precipitation curve (WPC) is essential to anticipate potential solutions for this problem. The determination of both WAT and WPC requires reliable data on the amount of precipitated wax and the trapped crude oil remaining in these mixtures. The estimation of the latter is difficult due to the scarcity of experimental methodologies.

In this work, a method based on differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was developed to determine the trapped crude oil of precipitated mixtures. The WPC were experimentally determined by fractional precipitation and DSC analysis for a variety of crude oils. The comparison of these curves requires the correction of the former by subtracting the trapped crude oil remaining in the precipitated mixtures. The trapped crude oil was calculated using two methods: one based on proton nuclear magnetic resonance (^1H NMR) previously developed and other based on DSC, developed in this work. This method considers that the gel formed when decreasing the temperature contains not only solids, but also occluded crude oil. The values of trapped crude oil estimated by both methods were used to correct experimental WPC. The comparison between corrected WPC and those ones obtained by DSC analysis showed the superiority of DSC over ^1H NMR to calculate the amount of trapped crude oil.

Keywords: Fractional precipitation, wax precipitation curve, wax porosity, differential scanning calorimetry.

1. Introduction

Paraffinic waxes present in petroleum crude oils can precipitate when temperature decreases during production, transport through pipelines or storage. The accumulation of solids on the walls can affect pipelines and equipment, increasing the cost of pumping, reducing or even stopping the production¹⁻⁵. For that, the knowledge of solid formation conditions is crucial to avoid economical consequences. Therefore, the prediction of wax appearance conditions is required to evaluate the risk of wax precipitation and to anticipate solutions for future problems in wells.

The quantification of wax precipitation requires the wax appearance temperature (WAT) and the amount of wax formed as a function of the temperature (wax precipitation curve, WPC). The prediction of these magnitudes is frequently carried out by thermodynamic models⁶⁻¹³, but their application is limited due to the scarcity of reliable experimental information¹⁴.

The experimental determination of the WAT and the WPC is well reported in the literature¹⁵⁻¹⁷, although most of the methods show limitations to determine the WPC due to the use of solvents. This reduces the available experimental information, needed to compare these results with those obtained by techniques such as differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)¹⁸⁻²¹, Nuclear Magnetic Resonance spectroscopy (NMR)²² and Fourier Transformed Infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR)^{23, 24}. To overcome these limitations, a method based on fractional wax precipitation has been recently developed²⁵. This method allows the WAT and the WPC to be determined from non diluted crude oils, thus avoiding the solvent effect. However, some considerations about the amount of precipitated wax should be made since the trapped crude oil (commonly described as wax porosity) remaining within the precipitated wax has to be considered.

It is well known that significant amounts of crude oil can have a noticeable effect on the total amount of the gel formed, and therefore it should be determined and included in the predictive models. Although the experimental determination of trapped crude oil is not well established, there are several techniques, which potentially could be used. Thus, a method based on ^1H NMR has been recently developed and applied to different crude oils^{26, 27}. In this method, aromatic hydrogen atoms are assumed to be only due to the presence of trapped oil. By comparing the amount of aromatic hydrogen atoms in each precipitated fraction with that in the raw crude oil, it is possible to estimate the content of the entrapped crude oil. However, it has been shown that this method presents important uncertainties, yielding unreliable results.

The aim of this work is to check the capabilities of DSC analysis to determine the crude oil occluded in fractions precipitated from different crude oils. The WPC for a variety of crude oils was obtained by both the fractional precipitation method mentioned above²⁵ and by DSC²¹. The results obtained by these methods can not be directly compared due to the entrapped crude oil. In this work, this magnitude was calculated by ^1H NMR spectroscopy and DSC analysis for each precipitated fraction. The calculated values were used to obtain the true amount of wax precipitated at each temperature, thus correcting the experimental WPC. Corrected WPC were compared to those ones obtained by DSC, showing better agreement for those corrected using DSC analysis to determine the trapped crude oil.

2. Experimental Section

Crude oils. A variety of water-free, gas-free crude oils summarized in Table 1 and provided by Repsol were used in this work.

Fractional precipitation. The experimental method is based on a filtration process at controlled temperature and has been previously reported in the literature²⁵. A sample of

crude oil is cooled in a cryostat at a slightly higher temperature than its WAT (previously determined by DSC analysis) for 24 h. The sample is then filtered using a glass microfiber for at least 2 h. The solid phase is washed down with acetone to reduce the trapped crude oil and then is recovered by solution in dichloromethane. This procedure can be repeated 4 or 5 times by decreasing the temperature at each step.

Wax Content. The amount of paraffin waxes precipitated at -20 °C was determined following a modification ²⁵ of the method reported by Burger et al.¹⁵ The crude oil is dissolved in n-pentane and stirred during 30 min. Acetone is added to the mixture (acetone/n-pentane ratio of 3:1) and cooled to -20°C for 24 h. The solid phase is separated by filtration in a Buchner funnel using a glass microfibre Whatman Filter No. 934. The solid phase is redissolved in n-hexane to remove asphaltenes. After solvent removal, the final product is weighted.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). The differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) technique is widely used to carry out the experimental determination and quantification of wax precipitation ¹⁸⁻²¹. This technique has the advantage of its simplicity and fast response which make it appropriate to develop routine essays. In DSC analysis a crude oil sample follows a temperature profile and heat transfer is registered so that phase transition can be quantified because the heat change involved. The application to crude oil samples requires solving experimental difficulties: the signals are broad and with low-intensity, high sensitivity is required, the determination of the base line is quite complex, the integration of the thermogram is not clearly defined, etc.

In this work, the experimental apparatus used was a DSC Mettler-Toledo DSC822e. The following temperature profile reported by Coto et al. ²¹ was used to obtain both WAT and WPC:

- Sample is heated at 3°C/min from 25 to 80°C to completely dissolve possible solid phase and to remove any thermal history. This temperature is held for 2 min.
- Sample is cooled down from 80 to -120 °C at 3°C/min.
- Sample is heated up from -120 to 80 °C at 3°C/min.

This procedure was used to obtain the cooling thermograms of the mixtures. Coto et al.²¹ propose a method to integrate DSC signal by drawing a baseline which can not be considered as a straight line due to the wide temperature range taken into account for DSC analysis. This procedure assumes that the sample behaves as a usual liquid at temperatures above the WAT and as a solid at very low temperature. In both extreme temperature ranges, the heat flow is exclusively related to the heating/cooling of a one phase system and it can be fitted to a second order polynomial function representing the heat capacity of the system²¹. The difference between the DSC curve and the baseline is a direct measurement of the total heat involved in the phase change and can be converted into the corresponding mass, by means of the specific melting heat. In this work, the cooling process is studied, so the amount of precipitated material can be determined at each temperature, yielding the WPC.

¹H NMR Spectroscopy. A Varian Mercury Plus NMR spectrometer (C/H dual 5 mm probe, frequency of 400 MHz) was used to quantify the different types of hydrogen atoms. Samples were dissolved in CDCl₃ in 5 mm sample tubes. The number of scans was 64, with a 30° pulse and a 1s delay time between scans.

The trapped crude oil of the samples was determined by ¹H NMR spectroscopy following a procedure reported elsewhere²⁶.

3. Determination of wax porosity.

As reported in the literature, the determination of trapped crude oil (wax porosity) can be carried out by ^1H NMR analysis^{26, 27}. However, this method presents uncertainties and limitations, and therefore other techniques must be investigated to obtain more realistic results. In this work, the trapped crude oil was determined by both ^1H NMR and DSC analysis.

^1H NMR analysis. This method, developed by Martos et al.²⁶, assumes that wax contains a negligible amount of aromatic hydrogen atoms, and therefore they are only due to the presence of trapped oil. Thus, an estimation of the content of the entrapped crude oil or wax porosity can be obtained, considering the paraffin solid previously separated at each temperature during the fractional precipitation process. Therefore, the trapped crude or porosity (ε) in wt. % for each mixture can be estimated as follows:

$$\varepsilon(\text{wt.}\%) = 100 - \left(\frac{H_{arC} - H_{arS}}{H_{arC}} \cdot 100 \right) \quad (1)$$

where H_{ar} denotes the content of aromatic hydrogen atoms (in wt.%); C and S subscripts refer to Crude oil and Precipitated sample, respectively.

DSC analysis. In this work, a new procedure based on DSC experimental technique was used to determine the trapped crude oil of the precipitated mixtures. For each precipitated fraction (i) the following mass balance can be considered:

$$\text{Fraction}_i : P_i \cdot y_i = P_i(1 - \varepsilon_i) + P_i \cdot \varepsilon_i \cdot x_i \quad (2)$$

where,

P_i : Mass of the precipitated fraction.

ε_i : Wax porosity.

y_i : Total paraffin fraction (wt.) of each precipitated fraction obtained by DSC analysis. It is assumed to be the highest value of wax content in the WPC obtained by DSC. This value is usually accepted to be the one at -20°C ¹⁴, since waxes precipitated at lower

temperatures are not considered in flow assurance problems (as they are lighter than C₂₀₊)²⁵.

x_i : Paraffin fraction (wt.) of the crude oil trapped in each fraction, which can be calculated as follows:

$$x_i = x_0 - z_i \quad (3)$$

where,

x_0 : Total paraffin fraction (wt.) obtained by DSC analysis of the raw crude oil.

z_i : Paraffin fraction (wt.) of the raw crude oil obtained by DSC analysis at the precipitation temperature.

As an example, in Figure 1 the WPC of a precipitated fraction and that of a crude oil is depicted, indicating the variables (y_i , x_0 and z_i) described above.

From eq. 2, the following relationship can be obtained for the wax porosity (ε_i):

$$\varepsilon_i = \frac{1 - y_i}{1 - x_i} \quad (4)$$

Consequently, two DSC analyses are required: one for the raw crude oil and a second one for the precipitated fraction.

In some cases, x_i can be considered negligible, and therefore the wax porosity can be calculated as follows:

$$\varepsilon_i = 1 - y_i \quad (5)$$

For the application of this simplified method only the DSC analysis for the precipitated fraction is required.

4. Results and discussion

Wax precipitation curve. The WPC of each crude oil was experimentally obtained by fractional precipitation and by DSC analysis following the procedures reported by Coto et al.^{21,25}, respectively.

WPC obtained by fractional precipitation and DSC analysis are compared in Figure 2. As can be seen, the amount of precipitated solid obtained by fractional precipitation is clearly higher than the one obtained by DSC analysis, due to the presence of trapped crude oil in the precipitated fractions^{14, 26, 27}. This affects to the fractional precipitation results but not to the DSC ones where only phase transitions are detected. Consequently, the results obtained by both techniques can not be straightforward compared.

Wax porosity.The trapped crude oil (wax porosity) was calculated for each fraction using the methods described above.

Table 2 shows the precipitated fractions at different temperatures for each crude oil, the amount of precipitated solid at each temperature and the wax porosity values determined by ¹H NMR analysis. These results reveal that precipitated mixtures are mainly composed of crude oil, in agreement with the results reported elsewhere^{14, 26, 27}. However, these values should be considered with caution, as this method presents an important limitation because petroleum mixtures shows very low signal/noise ratio for H_{ar}. This introduces important errors in the quantification of the trapped crude oil as reported by Martos et al²⁶.

Table 3 summarizes the precipitated fractions at different temperatures for each crude oil, the parameters required to calculate the wax porosity and the values of this magnitude determined by eq. 4. As stated before, the results reveal that precipitated fractions are mainly composed of raw crude oil.

Figure 3 shows the wax porosity values calculated by ¹H NMR and DSC analysis (using both eq. 4 and 5) for crude oil B (medium paraffinic). As can be seen, similar values of wax porosity were obtained by the different methods, showing their consistency for most of the precipitation temperatures. Similar results were obtained for other crude oils

except for the highly paraffinic oils, where remarkable differences between DSC values and those obtained by ^1H NMR were found.

In order to check the reliability of the studied methods, the experimental WPC (Figure 2) was corrected with the trapped crude oil values obtained by ^1H NMR and DSC (eq. 4 and 5) analysis. The corrected WPC were compared to those experimentally determined as shown in Figure 4. Similar values of wax porosity were obtained by DSC (eq. 4 and 5) and $^1\text{HNMR}$ for most of the crude oils. However, discrepancies were found for crude oils A and C. In these cases, the correction made to the WPC using eq. 4 is clearly superior to that obtained by ^1H NMR and DSC (eq. 5).

This indicates that the simplification assumed in eq. 5 can be correctly used for crude oils with low/medium paraffin content. Nevertheless, the results yielded by eq. 4 should be more realistic for highly paraffinic crude oils, as x_i can not be assumed to be negligible.

To determine the deviations between the WPC obtained by DSC and those obtained after correcting experimental WPC using the wax porosity calculated by DSC and $^1\text{HNMR}$ methods, the standard average deviation was calculated, as follows:

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum \delta_i^2}{n-1}} \quad (6)$$

$$\delta_i = (\text{solid wt\%})_{DSC\ WPC} - (\text{solid wt\%})_{Corrected\ WPC} \quad (7)$$

where,

n : Number of precipitated samples and the Σ is extended over those n samples for each crude oil.

Table 4 shows the wax porosity values for the studied crude oils determined by the three methods reported in this work. In general, lower deviations were obtained for the WPC corrected using DSC than those obtained when using ^1H NMR correction. For highly

paraffinic crude oils (A and C), higher deviations were obtained by ^1H NMR and DSC (eq. 5), thus being the most reliable results those yielded by eq. 4. However, for the rest of crude oils (with lower content of paraffins) similar results were obtained by all methods, being slightly superior those ones using DSC (eq. 5).

4. Conclusions

Precipitated fractions from crude oils are mainly composed of trapped crude oil, regardless the different chemical nature (paraffinic or naphthenic) of the crude oil.

The trapped crude oil in waxy mixtures precipitated from crude oils can be determined by DSC and ^1H NMR analysis.

DSC analysis can be used to estimate the trapped crude oil in precipitated fractions from crude oils with high and low wax content. For highly paraffinic crude oils lower deviations were obtained using eq. 4 (extended method) than those determined by eq. 5 (simplified method), revealing that is necessary to consider the amount of wax belonging to the raw crude oil. On the contrary, the wax porosity results for lower paraffin content allow using eq. 5.

The comparison between ^1H NMR and DSC methods shows the superiority of the latter to accurately determine wax porosity for crude oils with high or low wax content.

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Nomenclature

Abbreviations

H_{arC} : Content of aromatic hydrogen in the crude oil (wt.%).

H_{arS} : Content of aromatic hydrogen in the precipitated fraction (wt. %)

P_i : weight of the precipitated fraction.

x_0 : Total paraffin fraction (wt.) obtained by DSC analysis of the raw crude oil.

x_i : Paraffin fraction (wt.) of the crude oil trapped in each sample

y_i : Total paraffin fraction (wt.) of each precipitated fraction obtained by DSC analysis.

z_i : Paraffin fraction (wt.) of raw crude oil obtained by DSC analysis at the precipitation temperature.

Symbols

ε : Wax porosity (trapped crude oil) (wt. %).

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Figure captions

Figure 1. Parameters required for calculating wax porosity by DSC methods.

Figure 2. WPC obtained by fractional precipitation (\blacktriangle) and by DSC (—) analysis for the studied crude oils

Figure 3. Wax porosity of crude oil B calculated by the studied methods: $^1\text{H NMR}$ (Δ); DSC (eq.4) (\circ) and DSC (eq.5) (\square).

Figure 4. Comparison between experimental WPC obtained by DSC (—) and WPC obtained by fractional precipitation and corrected by $^1\text{HNMR}$ (Δ), DSC (eq.4) (\circ) DSC (eq.5) (\square).

Table 1. Crude oils used in this work.

<i>Crude oil</i>	<i>Origin</i>	<i>Nature</i>
A	North Sea	Paraffinic
B	West Africa	Paraffinic
C	West Africa	Paraffinic
D	Middle East	Paraffinic
E	South America	Naphthenic
F	South America	Naphthenic

Table 2. Trapped crude oil calculated by ^1H NMR for the precipitated mixtures.

<i>Fraction</i>	<i>T</i> ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	<i>Precipitated solid</i> (wt. %)	<i>Har</i> (wt. %)	ϵ_{NMR} (wt. %)
<i>Crude oil A</i>	-	-	3.9	-
<i>A1</i>	30	1.1	3.2	81
<i>A2</i>	25	2.8	3.4	87
<i>A3</i>	20	5.2	3.2	82
<i>A4</i>	15	7.2	3.4	87
<i>A5</i>	10	12.3	3.6	93
<i>Crude oil B</i>	-	-	3.6	-
<i>B1</i>	10	0.1	3.5	97
<i>B2</i>	5	0.4	2.3	64
<i>B3</i>	0	2.2	2.3	64
<i>B4</i>	-5	2.6	1.4	40
<i>B5</i>	-10	3.0	1.8	51
<i>B6</i>	-15	3.5	2.0	56
<i>B7</i>	-20	4.1	1.6	44
<i>B8</i>	-25	5.1	2.5	71
<i>B9</i>	-30	5.6	1.5	41
<i>Crude oil C</i>	-	-	4.0	-
<i>C1</i>	30	3.8	3.7	93
<i>C2</i>	25	7.3	3.7	89
<i>C3</i>	20	11.0	3.6	91
<i>C4</i>	17	23.1	3.8	97
<i>Crude oil D</i>	-	-	4.9	-
<i>D1</i>	40	0.5	4.7	96
<i>D2</i>	35	1.5	4.7	95
<i>D3</i>	30	2.2	4.7	95
<i>D4</i>	25	3.0	4.6	94
<i>D5</i>	20	3.7	4.6	92
<i>D6</i>	15	4.5	4.3	87
<i>D7</i>	10	5.3	3.9	80
<i>D8</i>	5	6.1	3.8	76
<i>D9</i>	0	7.9	4.2	85
<i>D10</i>	-5	9.6	4.4	90
<i>Crude oil E</i>	-	-	5.3	-
<i>E1</i>	25	1.3	5.3	98
<i>E2</i>	20	3.2	5.2	98
<i>E3</i>	15	4.9	5.2	97
<i>E4</i>	10	8.3	5.1	96
<i>E5</i>	5	10.9	5.3	99
<i>Crude oil F</i>	-	-	5.5	-
<i>F1</i>	20	1.0	5.3	98
<i>F2</i>	15	2.0	5.0	91
<i>F3</i>	10	3.4	4.9	89
<i>F4</i>	5	5.3	5.1	94
<i>F5</i>	0	8.0	5.5	99
<i>F6</i>	-5	8.6	4.8	88

Table 3. Trapped crude oil calculated by DSC for the precipitated mixtures.

<i>Fraction</i>	<i>T</i> (°C)	<i>x</i> ₀ (wt. %)	<i>z</i> _{<i>i</i>} (wt. %)	<i>x</i> _{<i>i</i>} (wt. %)	<i>y</i> _{<i>i</i>} (wt. %)	<i>ε</i> _{eq,4} (wt. %)
<i>Crude oil A</i>	-	4.4	-	-	-	-
<i>A1</i>	30		0.1	4.3	11.0	93
<i>A2</i>	25		0.2	4.2	10.8	93
<i>A3</i>	20		0.4	4.0	8.9	95
<i>A4</i>	15		0.7	3.7	10.8	93
<i>A5</i>	10		1.0	3.4	10.4	93
<i>Crude oil B</i>	-	1.6	-	-	-	-
<i>B1</i>	10		0.0	1.6	8.5	93
<i>B2</i>	5		0.0	1.6	31.1	70
<i>B3</i>	0		0.2	1.4	36.8	64
<i>B4</i>	-5		0.5	1.1	41.1	60
<i>B5</i>	-10		0.9	0.7	50.6	50
<i>B6</i>	-15		1.2	0.4	35.3	65
<i>B7</i>	-20		1.6	0.0	42.5	57
<i>B8</i>	-25		2.0	0.0	17.1	83
<i>B9</i>	-30		2.4	0.0	47.4	52
<i>Crude oil C</i>	-	4.9	-	-	-	-
<i>C1</i>	30		0.1	4.8	8.1	97
<i>C2</i>	25		0.3	4.6	8.0	96
<i>C3</i>	20		0.7	4.2	7.9	96
<i>C4</i>	17		1.0	3.9	8.1	96
<i>Crude oil D</i>	-	3.0	-	-	-	-
<i>D1</i>	40		0.0	3.0	6.7	96
<i>D2</i>	35		0.0	3.0	5.8	97
<i>D3</i>	30		0.0	3.0	7.0	96
<i>D4</i>	25		0.0	3.0	7.4	95
<i>D5</i>	20		0.1	2.9	9.7	93
<i>D6</i>	15		0.3	2.7	18.9	83
<i>D7</i>	10		0.5	2.5	17.5	85
<i>D8</i>	5		0.8	2.2	14.6	87
<i>D9</i>	0		1.2	1.8	17.4	84
<i>D10</i>	-5		1.7	1.3	11.0	90
<i>Crude oil E</i>	-	1.3	-	-	-	-
<i>E1</i>	25		0.0	1.3	2.5	99
<i>E2</i>	20		0.0	1.3	2.7	99
<i>E3</i>	15		0.1	1.3	2.4	99
<i>E4</i>	10		0.2	1.1	2.8	98
<i>E5</i>	5		0.4	1.0	3.9	97
<i>Crude oil F</i>	-	1.3	-	-	-	-
<i>F1</i>	20		0.0	1.3	5.1	96
<i>F2</i>	15		0.1	1.3	4.1	97
<i>F3</i>	10		0.2	1.1	5.0	96
<i>F4</i>	5		0.4	0.9	3.8	97
<i>F5</i>	0		0.6	0.7	3.7	97
<i>F6</i>	-5		0.8	0.5	2.6	98

Table 4. Standard average deviation for the trapped crude oil values obtained by DSC and ¹HNMR methods.

<i>Crude oil</i>	$\sigma_{eq.4}$	$\sigma_{eq.7}$	σ_{HNMR}
A	0.14	0.37	0.44
B	0.30	0.30	0.29
C	0.16	0.55	0.49
D	0.26	0.19	0.19
E	0.10	0.07	0.07
F	0.33	0.25	0.20

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

